

**WHATSAPP VOICE CHAT (WVC) AS AN EFL ONLINE
LEARNING MEDIA**

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Abstract: In recent years, researcher interested in mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) for online learning of English as a foreign language (EFL). In the current era of digitalization, access to information and materials can be easily found in cyberspace, either by accessing a page or by using an application. With these advances in technology, can be used as a tool to facilitate the educational process. The Ministry of Education and Culture is aware of the current needs, because by utilizing technology it can reach and distribute broad policies, as well as optimize the implementation of the Merdeka curriculum. As a teacher, this is a challenge in itself to bring students to learning transformation, where the teacher acts as a facilitator to encourage the learning process.

Key Words: Whatsapp, Online learning, Media

INTRODUCTION

In the era of the development of science and technology, language is one thing that cannot be separated from the role of human life. With language we can express emotions, ideas, and desires. Language is also used as a medium or tool to communicate with others. One of the most important languages to learn is English. The reason why it is important to learn English is because English is an international language.

Given the importance of English proficiency, many countries, including Indonesia, make English the primary subject taught in schools.

In recent years, researcher interested in mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) for online learning of English as a foreign language (EFL). In the current era of digitalization, access to information and materials can be easily found in cyberspace, either by accessing a page or by using an application. With these advances in technology, can be used as a tool to facilitate the educational process. The Ministry of Education and Culture is aware of the current needs, because by utilizing technology it can reach and distribute broad policies, as well as optimize the implementation of the Merdeka curriculum. As a teacher, this is a challenge in itself to bring students to learning transformation, where the teacher acts as a facilitator to encourage the learning process (Insiyah, 2018).

Technology that applied in online learning to help students increase in out-of-class language learning experiences (Lai and Gu, 2011). Learning outside the classroom using mobile phones is "the richest vein of language learning potential, in that students may engage in a variety of informal learning activities: incidental (e.g., gameplay), instrumental (e.g., use of a language learning service or app), or accidental (e.g., code-switching in a YouTube video)" (Godwin-Jones, 2017). Using this type of audiovisual technology, sources of original language input for either formal or informal learning can be easily found by learners of both English as a second language (ESL) and a foreign language (EFL).

In today's technological developments and new curriculum, it demands teachers to be more creative in choosing the right media in the teaching and learning process. In the media taxonomy, Rudi Breetz

divides eight media classifications, namely dynamic audiovisual media, silent audiovisual media, semi-dynamic sound, animation, still images, semi-animation, sound and printing (Sadiman, 2021). In giving learning activity to students, they must also use appropriate and varied media, by avoiding boredom for students. One of the media that can be used is social media. Social media is a potentially power tool in education (Almodiel, 2017). Social media is an example of technological developments that are useful in the world of education if used with the right methods. One of the social media that the researchers focused on in this research was called Whatsapp.

In the context of learning a foreign language, the acquisition of speaking skills is imperative, especially in the case of learning English. Effectively communicating in English is a crucial aspect of language acquisition, and the teacher experienced the repercussions of this during in-person meetings. According to Brown (2000), the demonstration of an ability to achieve practical goals through interactive dialogue with other speakers is a key indicator of successfully acquiring a language. Therefore, speaking plays a vital role in learning English as a foreign language, enabling learners to effectively communicate in the target language and achieve their language learning goals.

Widad (2021) with his research which discussed testing the challenges of teaching in a virtual classroom using Whatsapp during a pandemic. The researcher used a qualitative descriptive method with the subject of three English teachers and eight MA Darul Falah students, Cermee Bondowoso. In the study it was concluded that there were several challenges faced by students and teachers in virtual classrooms using

Whatsapp during the pandemic such as unstable internet networks, different telephone capacities, and lack of interaction between teachers and students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Nature of MALL

Mobile phones with advanced capabilities have expanded into all aspects of human existence, including language learning. Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) is the application of mobile technologies to language acquisition (Tayabeh and Amin, 2012). The use of mobile phone in learning language makes the learning become intuitive, informal, individual, and flexible. Convenience features and specifications such as being easy to carry everywhere, the pad design (keypad or touchpad) and audio feature makes mobile phone become potential media in learning language environment. Tayabeh and Amin (2012) also added in learning language environment, mobile phone provides extensive learning, such as giving more chance to learning, varied learning, and private learning, Although not all learning content and activities are mobile phone accessible. Mobile phone can facilitate some activities of language learning such as game-based learning, chat-based learning, find word and pronunciation challenge, etc. Those activities are able to facilitate language learning for speaking, vocabulary, listening, grammar, and reading. Besides that, there is also a disadvantage in using mobile phones in language learning. For example, less specification, limited capacity of storage, and processor speed.

In addition, Stockwell and Hubbard (2013) propose several principles for the use of MALL. The principles are as follows:

1. Mobile activity, task and apps should be adjusted with the limitation of device and environment.
2. It should limit multitasking and environmental distractions.
3. The use of a mobile device also needs to respect learner's time.
4. Strive to maintain equity.
5. Acknowledge and plan for accommodating language learner differences.
6. Be aware of the language learner's perception of their mobile device use.
7. Design an activity and task short and succinct.
8. Let the task fit with technology and environment.
9. Consider that sometimes learners need to be given guidance in using a mobile device for educational purposes.

The Use of Voice Chat in MALL

Mobile phones supports various activity related to language learning which can name SMS, camera, audio/video recording, internet access, camera and audio/video messaging. There are many activities can

be facilitated by MALL. One of the activities is voice messaging/chat. Voice chat is available inside the social media application which can use for learning language. Related to this research which uses voice chat as media English online learning for EFL student.

In addition, there is a reason why the use of voice chat in online learning English recommended. First, because it easy to use. Second, it can be interactive activity between the students and teacher. Moreover, voice chat can be a media without the limitation of learning place and time.

The Nature of Whatsapp

The emergence of communication of technology has tremendous effect on the field of EFL learning at synchronous and asynchronous or hybrid learning, especially in covid and pasca covid era. One of the technological applications which familiarly used by teacher and student in Indonesia is Whatsapp Messenger and Zoom Meeting due to the application is user friendly, and accommodated the speaking class by Voice Note Messenger.

This application allows users to send document files, photo files, video calls, GPS locations and others. This application also has broadcast and group message features making it easier for users to condition several other users in one group. So that this can be used in the world of education, namely by creating a Whatsapp group as a class group. According Nurazizah et al., (2019) stated that the use of WhatsApp as a potential online media to practice students' speaking skills, where students can record voices and then send recordings their votes to the WhatsApp group.

Whatsapp also has a message status in the form of a sign that functions to find out the status of the message, so that teachers can monitor students whether they have opened, read or not at all. Whatsapp is also a cross-platform message which is one of the alternative tools or communication media that is widely used by the world of education, especially schools today, plus the WhatsApp application also provides a group chat feature to make it easier to discuss or provide information through groups. some people use the Whatsapp application to share news, exchange ideas, discuss various information on the world of lectures or information outside campus or just joke with each other between friends. Whatsapp is also very integrated with subjects, such as English lessons. Whatsapp provides one feature that can allow teachers to teach speaking skills, namely the voice message feature.

The Utilization of Whatsaap

Technically, WhatsApp provided for quick access to the information. The program's straightforward operation concepts make it accessible to a wide range of users from various ages and backgrounds. Bhounik and Deshen (2014) stated “Anyone having a smartphone, an active internet connection, and the WhatsApp software installed can communicate with anyone”.

Voice Message is one of the many services that WhatsApp offers to make it simple for users to interact with one another. This function allows users to rapidly speak with contacts and groups. It offers a richer chat experience and can be used to transmit crucial and urgent information. Automatic download of this voice message feature occurs.

WhatsApp may be utilized as an English learning tool with this simple process. The teacher can creatively use this program by talking about various motions, providing discussion-worthy photographs, and even using Voice Messages to hear each other's voices. The usage of WhatsApp allows students to express themselves freely without feeling self-conscious, which improves language learning and English competence. WhatsApp's adaptability has the potential to meet a variety of learning demands in English, particularly in regular communication.

The teachers' role in using WhatsApp as a language learning tool is that of an examiner who assists in correcting and commenting on the students' responses and takes an active position in the conversation (Mistar, 2016).

The Advantage and Disadvantage of Whatsapp

There are some basic considerations why social media is used in the process of learning. In addition, Gon and Rawekar (2017) note that "as of today, it seems that WhatsApp has advantages over other technology devices employed by the education system, such as low cost, simplicity, accessibility, and efficiency." Students are familiar with technology, so it can be a substitute device to offer new learning experiences for students (Kheryadi, 2017).

1) Advantage of Whatsapp

a) The contact of the telephone is automatically synchronized. Because contacts from the phonebook are instantly connected to Whatsapp, users can connect with friends who are already in contact more easily. Similarly, when using the Whatsapp app, our contact

numbers that are already registered on the service will be instantly linked to a friend's account.

b) The easiest to register this application. The registration requirement also just uses the telephone number that is used.

c) The easiest to set up, this advantage is different from the other application messages. Users of WhatsApp can customize the chat room's display backdrop. Users won't get tired of the WhatsApp app's appearance as a result.

d) The WhatsApp instant messaging makes it simple to create and share information and knowledge (Bahroumi, 2015).

e) The usage of WVC give the students a chance to express their performance without feeling shy.

f) The WVC can allows the students to evaluate by repeating their voice chat performance, so the students know about their weakness.

g) The WFC can allows the teacher directly give feedback to the students' performances, so the students can practice and fix their English.

2) Disadvantage of Whatsapp

a) To access real-time information, teachers and students need to be online.

b) To impacted by communication, that uses videos, photos, and huge files using data.

c) To communicate may get out from the context of learning, without explicit guidelines

or agreements from group administrators (educators), (Pustikayasa, 2019).

EFL Online Activity Setting

EFL online activity setting means that the activity provides individualized allows teachers to teach students with varying backgrounds, such as language ability and learning achievements (Soliman, 2016). While the teacher can reach each students in class and provide rapid feedback, the online setting allows students to learn a foreign language at their own pace, regardless of time or location. Students gain autonomy through online learning by learning on their own (Eneau & Develotte, 2012). As a result, online learning can help EFL students establish learner autonomy, improve their learning attitudes and involvement levels, and boost their confidence and commitment (Kim & Yoon, 2021).

All learning subjects can be taught online such as English. According to Perveen (2016), online learning is an effective medium for English language learning since it allows for the use of a variety of teaching methods, learning styles, and methods. In particular, online learning has been popular as an alternate strategy to teaching and learning in higher education institutions (Famularsih, 2020). The most important aspects of online learning is to know how the implementation online learning itself on their learning experience. Therefore, this research figures out online learning focusing on the use of online media.

The Use of Whatsapp Voice Chat (WVC) in EFL Online Learning

Whatsapp voice chat (WVC) is one of the features of the Whatsapp Messenger Application which is very often used by users because it is easy to use. According to Hanum & Subrata (2021), the WVC feature makes it easy for users to communicate instantly with contacts and groups via voice recordings. In addition, this feature provides a real chat experience and people can use it to convey important factual information. In this research, WVC can be used as an idea to practice EFL students' speaking.

How to use it is the same as the default voice recording application from a mobile phone, but this feature has become a part of the Whatsapp Messenger application, so no need the default voice recording application anymore. So that, This research used procedure adapted from Alireza, Hassan and Karim (2014) research with some modification in implementing Audio-Recorded in speaking for EFL. First, the teacher explained the instructions, so the students understood what they should do. Second, the teacher gave the example of the task. The example can be the way teacher pronounced the sentences so the students have motivation in learning English.

After that, the students will record the audio of some sentences with certain materials. The materials related to teaching and learning in the class and also students' experience so the ide can be authentic. After the students sent their voice, the teacher give feedback on the studentsperformance. So that, the students' know their weakness in English especially speaking skill.

CONCLUSION

In the era of the development of science and technology, language is one thing that cannot be separated from the role of human life. With language we can express emotions, ideas, and desires. Language is also used as a medium or tool to communicate with others. One of the most important languages to learn is English. The reason why it is important to learn English is because English is an international language. Given the importance of English proficiency, many countries, including Indonesia, make English the primary subject taught in schools.

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